

Location

A large commercial complex building in Wuhan, China

Innovation

Multi-modal Autonomous Waste Sorting Robot (integrating 3D Vision, Spectral Analysis, and Mobile Manipulation)

Partners

Huazhong University of Science and Technology (HUST)
China Construction Third Bureau First Engineer Co., LTD

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

Data

RGB-D imagery, 3D LiDAR point clouds, NIR spectral data (900-1700nm), and JSON-encapsulated task/result frames.

Tools

ROS 1 (navigation/SLAM), STM32 (real-time execution), YOLOv8/v11 (perception), and MoveIt (manipulation).

Communication

HTTP/WebSocket via Wi-Fi and Bluetooth.

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This demo deploys an autonomous mobile robot for real-time, on-site construction and demolition (C&D) waste sorting. By integrating YOLOv8 visual detection with Near-Infrared (NIR) material verification, the system identifies and retrieves 6 key waste categories: concrete, metal, wood, plastic, mixed rubble, and hazardous materials. The goal is to replace hazardous manual sorting, reduce logistical costs of mixed waste transport, and achieve a 60% recycling rate.

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- **Perception:** Real-time 3D Oriented Bounding Box (OBB) generation on edge devices.
- **Accuracy:** Successful physicochemical verification of materials with similar visual textures (e.g., PET vs. PVC). Efficiency: Significant reduction in manual sorting hours and on-site waste volume.
- **Control:** 50Hz high-frequency PID motor control and slip-aware grasping.

IMPACT

IMAGES

CONTACTS

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